

Impact of Religiosity on Purchase of Beauty Products in Pakistan

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ABSTRACT: Religion is an integral component of Pakistani culture with a growing impact that cannot be belittled by advertisers. The purpose of this study is to understand the dominant purchase element and its impact over customer preferences when purchasing beauty products within the Pakistani market. Six independent variables were empirically studied to determine which one has the highest influence and thereby impact on customer preference when buying beauty products. Primary data was collected through questionnaires from 280 respondents in urban Karachi and regression analysis was run to determine the impact of Quality Assurance, Country of Origin, Social Recognition, Consumer Ethnocentrism, Unavailable Local Substitute, and Religiosity on Customer Preferences when purchasing beauty products. The relationship between religious conviction and states of mind toward international items shows that consumers are going to abstain from purchasing international brands out of a strong sense of religiosity. The study helps managers of beauty brands, a growing segment within the local market, to determine the elements that have the highest impact on customer preferences to better develop their product campaigns.

KEYTERMS: Quality Assurance, Country of Origin, Consumer ethnocentrism, Social Recognition, Religiosity, Beauty Products

1. INTRODUCTION

The study seeks to determine the impact of Quality Assurance, Country of Origin, Social Recognition, Consumer Ethnocentrism, Unavailable Local Substitute, and Religiosity on Customer Preferences while acquiring imported and local beauty care products to get a hold and boost in the sales and ultimately on profits by implying the mechanism best fit for the factors. Customer preference in this study comprises on the demand; willingness and ability of consumer to purchase products. As consumer now a days are well-informed and have more access to international products because of the globalization this definitely influence their preferences. The rise in purchasing power parity of Pakistan (World Bank, 2020) indicates that consumers are spending more on the products which provide liberty and personification to them. Shifting their preferences from local to imported products now a days is fairly easy as people are more brand conscious especially in the industry of beauty care they tend to attach themselves with those products which are from an eminent foreign brand.

Furthermore, higher import rates have also point towards the consumer involvement in imported products and the purpose of this study is to get the in-depth picture that which factor among all the independent variables has more influence on the customer preference. Since there is a boost in Islamic marketing in Pakistan and people here do consider the Halal factors while buying products so this also gives the exhaustive figure to international brands that how extensively this factor manipulates the preference and choice of the consumer while going for the purchase. The theory of planned behavior (Ajzen, 1991) emphasized over the fact that the behavior of humans is not 100% voluntary and in their control. However, it can be planned and deliberate over certain factors. The theory was thus provided to understand the deliberate behavior. The researcher have understood the factors by which the behavior of consumer is manipulated, because the behavior can be deliberate and planned. The motive of every organization is to generate profits, so the aim of this study is to understand the elements and their impact over customer preferences within the domestic market. We have explored that among all these independent variables which has a greater influences and has much impact on customer preference. The factors which have not been considered in the past have been comprehensively studied in this research and the relationship has also been tested. There are numerous studies conducted in the past to study various aspects of customer preferences, however, this study will add new perspective of the same thing by integrating the element of religiosity and its impact on a specific category of consumer purchase.

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2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The success and prosperity of any country depends upon its productivity of products and services. The world has become an international village and the organizations look to manufacture in house and then distribute its products internationally. The strength within the local environment and increased competition is a good sign for the country and it turns out to be a barrier for the international products to enter the arena. Moreover, even if there is an imported product available it wouldn't survive for long, which is the time when elements like consumer ethnocentrism, patriotism, country of origin come in existence. Furthermore, the local industries are much dependent on the consumers and their attitude towards their services. The moral duty and role of the consumers is to not let the local manufacturers suffer by preferring the foreign manufactured products.

The world is becoming increasingly complex and establishing an identity is indeed a core need for these small medium enterprises. Zimbabwe is one country which is suffering from a negative balance of payment and the government is coming up with different measures to prevent it from going further deep into it (The Herald, 2014). The many measures are proposed to support the local industries facing tough competition from the neighboring countries. Zimbabwe produces agricultural products but are still a large importer for South African products. Moreover, the consumer in the local arena claim high prices to be a factor of not opting for local products. The country is in a chaos, it is looking forward to save its local industries but on the expense of making the consumers suffer (The Herald, 2014). This suggests that it is not only the duty of the consumers to ensure the local industries do not lose out on their identity, but, it is a two-way relationship.

2.1 Customer preference

Customer preference for imported products has been widely discussed by marketing researchers. The consumer attitude is derived by some specific features in the product (Muhammad and Shah, 2011). Over the years it has been noticed that consumers are switching from purchasing the local products to the purchase of imported products. This is because of the availability of imported products in the local market, and the purchasing power of the consumer is increasing with the passage of time (CIA, 2016). However, there are other elements that have been selected for this research and a detailed focus will be presented.

A customer as an individual has different likes and dislikes, according to values, rituals, culture and a plethora of different factors. The behavior of an individual is not just the realm of economics but also the behavioral aspect plays a vital part. The purchase of a product is on the opportunity cost of the product they would have purchased instead. A definition of customer preferences states that the aim of these customers is to purchase a good which offers the maximum satisfaction level. However, customers are still limited by income, which bounds their purchase decision.

Preferences are also measured by the utility, of a combination of goods. It allows the customer to align the products according to the utility they have been receiving out of the purchase of these products. Customer preferences is a blend of different elements brought up together. Preferences for a product is undifferentiated by the prices and income. Moreover, the ability to purchase a product doesn't really determine the liking towards the product. A person can have a preference for Audi, but the financial resources have limited them to a Honda.

2.2 Consumer ethnocentrism

Consumer ethnocentrism is a concept which has been generally utilized as a part of examining buyers' mindset toward international products. It originates from the more broad idea of ethnocentrism, which thus is established in a conviction that one's own team is better than others. Consumer ethnocentrism is characterized by Nijssen as opinions held by buyers about the propriety or ethical quality of obtaining international items. Obtaining imported products is seen as incorrect as it will hurt the domestic economy, adverse effect unemployment, and is unpatriotic. They further came up with an estimation instrument, the CETSCALE, to survey these mentalities. Past studies have discovered high ethnocentrism scores are identified with hesitance to buy remote items and propensities to assess them contrarily (Nijssen, Douglas & Bressers, 2009).

A study by Boonghee and Naveen (2005), have stated in their study that people belonging from the developed countries tend to prefer their local products over the imported item. However, it is the opposite with the people living in the developing countries. The people in the developed countries have a positive feeling towards their locally made products because they believe that those products are culturally similar than those coming from foreign countries. Furthermore, the negative attitude of the people in the developing nations have impacted the local industries and thus posing a negative impression on the economy at large (Batra et.al, 2014).

Jiménez and Martín (2007) stated that consumer ethnocentrism can have a negative impact when an individual rates and evaluates the products before the re-purchase. However, they further emphasized that this may even vary amongst cultures depending upon the country of origin. They characterized consumer ethnocentrism as a faith apprehended by buyers on the

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correctness and undoubtedly profound quality of acquiring international products. Consumer ethnocentrism suggests the regulating trust that buying local products is more valuable than buying international products (Akdogan, et.al, 2012).

2.3 Unavailability of local substitutes

Substitute products can be defined in the neoclassical broad culture, everything can be traded and substituted with other things. Consumer products can substitute each other, even if not up to the mark. Everything can be purchased, as in whatever you have, it's constantly conceivable to discover alternative consumption packages that you would acknowledge as proportionate to your own (Dorman, 2014). In other words, money can purchase everything. This element can be easily understood by the term price elasticity of demand which is quite simple. The many possible substitutes there are for a particular product, the more projecting the elasticity. The time when there are limited substitutes accessible, shoppers have the room and space to alter their decision and select any of the better services or product offered because the cost is barely different. Alternately, if the substitute product is not available, the need would be inelastic and people will stick (Dorman, 2014).

Another element because of which consumers are likely to go for the purchase of foreign products is the unavailability of local substitutes. Especially in smaller countries, the domestic market is not large enough to stimulate domestic industry. If there is any internal options, for example, customers in countries without the automaker or home computers will have no choice but to buy imported goods. Therefore, clients are less inclined to have negative approaches towards foreign items. A study undertaken by Opoku et.al, (2009) stated that the products available from the local manufacturers are not diverse but demands are, which have forced them to opt for foreign products. The local industries must ensure that they increase the competitiveness of the domestic products to be acceptable within their markets.

This element can be easily understood by the term price elasticity of demand is quite simple. Substitutes are conceivable for this product, the elasticity is more prominent. At the time when some similar substitute, buyers can certainly vary from large, then the next, irrespective of the fact that there is only a small change in value. Alternatively, if no alternatives are available, interest in the product is likely to be inelastic (Dorman, 2014).

2.4 Quality

The quality of the products that are imported is indeed another element because of which the sales are relatively higher. The perception of customer is such that any product that has an international presence would be of superior quality. Researches have indicated that the consumers perceive global products as of high quality because of their prestigious image worldwide (Ismail, Masood & Tawab, 2012). The features of the products and their performance has proved their quality over the years. Quality perspective is divergent from manufactures based and item based methodology.

Product perceived quality specifically impacts to their expectation. Clients have a few observations about the item quality, prices and attributes before going to acquiring the item. Later, after utilizing of item, the preferences increases or decreases at the same time, in light of the fact that it has direct relations which influence. In the chance that the quality is high, the aim of client is likewise high. Authors proposed two contrasts between perceived quality and fulfillment. The clients considered perceived quality as a more particular idea taking into account item and services features (Bansal & Taylor, 2015). The organization can have a level of control over quality. In this way, it is recommended when perceived quality is viewed as general appraisals, then perceived quality is comprehended as the wellspring of fulfillment.

Quality is characterized by Saleem et.al as consumer finding related to a service or product performance and how this item contrasted with consumers' desire. Quality can likewise be characterized as the entire components and attributes of an item or services that bear on its capacity to fulfill expressed or suggested needs (2015). Many organizations affirm their quality depiction from business sector perspective. Buyer's impression of item quality is contrasted with expectation. Clients compute item quality as far as how much satisfaction they got from that item (Saleem et.al, 2015). On the other form, brand unwavering quality is assessed to affect the apparent quality of the item. Quality could be characterized as the customer finding around an item all in all matchless quality and incredibleness.

2.5 Country-of-origin

The products made available in any local market from an international market are particularly known by their country-of-origin, the marketing strategies are further developed in a way to promote the native country of the product. There are numerous examples, Sweden with cars, microelectronics are best produced by Japan, and French with fragrance and others (Kinra, 2006). However, if there is a negative stereotyping against the country, the brand will definitely be effected and vice versa. Furthermore, there are special cases for which country of origin doesn't really matter as the brands have a well establish name in the Global markets such as Audi, Toyota, Apple, and Google.

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Country of-origin (COO) can be characterized as any impact that the Country of producer has on a purchaser's certain or negative impression of an item (Yunus & Rashid, 2016). In point of interest, Azar et.al, 2014 expressed that COO is being seen like distinctive brands has a place with the diverse country. Those owning country are called Country of-origin. Researchers additionally discovered that country's image assume a critical part in purchaser's recognitions towards items and brands from any given country. Past study demonstrates that individuals think about which country the item originated from and where they were made (Parkvithee & Miranda 2012). The past investigation of the country of-origin impact has demonstrated how country's picture directly affects buy expectation.

Country of-origin is clearly the degree to which the manufacturing place impacts the buyers' judgment of the item. In this way, country of origin is among the imperative components that may impact the purchaser purchase expectation. Muslim nations are those nations that have a Muslim-dominant part populace like Malaysia, Saudi Arabia, and Pakistan and non-Muslim nations have Muslim-minority populaces, for example, China and France (Borzooei & Asgari, 2015). Therefore, there is a probability that country of origin (COO) could impact shoppers to separate between nations. The idea of COO includes the nation where the brand starts or is made. Country of origin or the "made in" mark is one of the fundamental assessment criteria in the obtaining choice (Borzooei & Asgari, 2015).

2.6 Social Recognition

A different perspective have also stated that consumer also prefer to buy foreign products because of products being associated with high prestige. The global brands are perceived to be having a high prestige because of their limited availability and high prices (Ismail, Masood & Tawab, 2012). Researches have also found out that consumers feel that their self-image is enhanced by acquiring these brands. However, De Mooij stated that local brands are produced after understanding the uniqueness of the local culture, still consumers are looking for a global product (2010).

Other opinions have stated that acquiring brands represents who the person is and how they want others to perceive them. There is an emotional connection with products, and people tend to view their self-image in products. The example of Apple users perfectly fit in this regards (Goldsmith, Flynn & Clark, 2011). There are also approaches which state that using some specific brands make other realize the economic background and a specific socioeconomic ladder the person belongs too. Further Goldsmith et.al stated that it permits them to feel as if they fit into society and have a place with the gathering. Wearing comparative and well-known brands helps us to identify with others in the gathering and feel a piece of an option that is bigger than themselves (2011).

2.7 Religiosity

Religious beliefs and understanding plays a vital role in the shaping the consumer behavior and how they go about their purchase decisions. The difference in religious affiliation influences the way people make their choices, what they eat and who they associate themselves (Shyan, Waller & Zafer, 2004). There are certain restrictions and limitations in every religion which is abided by the followers of that particular religion such as. Hindus do not consume beef, Muslims do not eat pork and do not drink alcohol. Marketers are now coming up with new ideas of advertising to these markets. These factors have had some serious implication for the brands coming from international markets involved in the production of pharmaceuticals, food, and cosmetics particularly (Mukhtar & Mohsin, 2012). There is regular conversation over the fact that whether Halal brands from Muslim nations or non-Muslim nations are the favored buyers' decisions.

To date, the production of halal brand is becoming a global industry. Halal element is a code of conduct in the life of a Muslim, and is an integral part to integrate it as part of their daily lives. It has been recognized and used all over the place and interest Halal brands of both Muslim and non-Muslim countries is growing rapidly on a distinctive part. It has been reviewed in the last centuries, the Muslim population is projected by alcanzar2.2billones world in 2030. It is expected that this important market will grow at a rate of seven percent per year and generate about \$ 1.5 billion (Alserhan, 2010). This remarkable growth in the global Halal market, in particular, food, called on Muslim and non-Muslim countries around the world to benefit from the huge potential and to enter the market to meet the Halal (Alserhan, 2010).

Each study is taken into account, looking for some leftovers in past studies that can work and present a new dimension of research to the audience. The same applies to the research that we do. There have been studies to talk about customer preferences for imported products at the local level of the past. Factors that researchers are taken into account, the amount of work done is minimal or negligible. Factor consumer ethnocentrism was used in most studies, and found in this study, too, only for the basic reason that the importance and value of an element, since it has a relatively large amount of exposure to Shaping with customer preferences. Nevertheless, the strength of the relationship is also seen in this particular missing in previous studies. In addition,

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this study also seeks to draw between all these variables that have the greatest impact on the development of customer preferences to opt for imports on local products.

3. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this research is to explore that which factors amongst quality assurance, country of origin, social recognition, consumer ethnocentrism, unavailable local Substitute and religiosity is more associated and has more impact on customer preference. In this study, the factors that are highly involved and have more control to influence the preference of the customers is studied. Primary data have collected through questionnaires and philosophy which we have used is positivism for our study and is quantitative, the deductive approach is used because we have tried to show the impact over dependent variables from independent and this have been explained by regression analysis, in contrast to this we've discussed the correlation and effects of different variables on the other, so to achieve that we have done explanatory research so have used mono method for that as it supports it. The research conducted is explanatory in nature and cross sectional study as this explicates the results for the specific period of time which might be differ in future.

There were various steps we incorporated to complete this study:

The initial part was to do a comprehensive research and select a topic which we did and selected "Explore the factors which determine customer preference towards local and imported beauty and personal healthcare products in Pakistan" as our topic for the study. The procedure followed is mention below.

1. After finalizing the topic, second thing we have done is to analyze the Gaps and find out the leftovers in the past which has not been studied yet.
2. Past researches were taken into account for finding the background of the dependent and independent variables and also for the purpose of doing the introduction and literature review.
3. After gathering plenty of information regarding the factors of our study research objectives have been generated to further carryout this study.
4. The next step was to prepare the research design based on the idea of research onion that consist of approaches, strategies, time horizon and data collection method.
5. After the initial designing of the questionnaire we had pilot test the questionnaire on a sample of 25 in order to check its reliability and to check the validity of our questionnaire we would get it checked by relevant industry expert.
6. Data has been collected via questionnaires which was float amongst an identified targeted audience those who are involve and the end user of the beauty care products either imported or local one's.

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7. The result that has been generated from the SPSS data includes frequency distribution, SD, correlation and regression.
8. Based on the result we have found out the acceptance or the rejection of our hypothesis.
9. Derived from the findings we have concluded and gave recommendations which might be useful for the brand managers and various stakeholders.

The participation was involved from the people residing in Karachi city who are involved in the purchasing of beauty care products. Population was varied for this study which has the age brackets between 20-45 year. The main emphasis has been on exploring the factors which determine customer preferences towards buying imported products and local products. According to the Pakistan demographics profile 2016, the total estimated population of Karachi is massive out of which around 48.6 percent are females, reaching all the participants would not be possible so we have used convenience based sampling to represent out over all population.

To conduct the study, we gathered the answers of the accessible population by defining the audience in the ratio of 20:80 Male | Female. The qualifier applied to identify the population was multivariate analysis. The study contains 1 Dependent and 6 Independent variables and according to the multivariate analysis for every variable 30 respondents were considered so, the total number of responses were $40 \times 7 = 280$ respondents.

5. HYPOTHESIS

Correlation

- H1: Quality assurance has a significant relationship with customer preference.
- H2: Country of Origin has a significant relationship with customer preference.
- H3: Social Recognition has a significant relationship with customer preference.
- H4: Consumer ethnocentrism has a significant relationship with customer preference.
- H5: Unavailable Local Substitutes significant relationship with customer preference.
- H6: Religiosity has a significant relationship with customer preference.

Regression

- H7: Quality assurance has a significant impact on customer preference.
- H8: Country of Origin has a significant impact on customer preference.
- H9: Social Recognition has a significant impact on customer preference.
- H10: Consumer ethnocentrism has a significant impact on customer preference.
- H11: Unavailable Local Subtitles has a significant impact on customer preference.
- H12: Religiosity has a significant impact on customer preference.

6. ANALYSIS & DISCUSSION

The aim of this study was to explore the factors which determine customer preference towards local and imported beauty and personal healthcare products in Pakistan. The data has been tested to check the reliability of the questionnaires and after that the descriptive analysis, correlation and regression have been checked on SPSS.

The questionnaire was designed after going through various definitions from books, multiple articles and discussions with supervisor and then pilot tested to assess the reliability of the construct. The reliability of the scale is 0.63 which is above 0.6; this shows that the scale is reliable and has internal consistency. Hence results attained from this questionnaire can be regarded as reliable. To check the reliability data has been taken from 30 respondents from the target audience.

All the correlations of independent variables except consumer ethnocentrism with Customer Preference are significant.

H1: Quality assurance has a significant relationship with customer preference.

The value of significance between quality assurance and customer Preference is 0.000 which is <0.05 , indicates that there is a relationship between these variable. The value of the correlation is .476 which suggests that the positive relationship between these variable is towards substantial side.

H2: Country of Origin has a significant relationship with customer preference.

The value of Significance for correlation between country of origin and customer preference is 0.000, therefore we have enough evidence to accept the alternate hypothesis that Country of Origin has a significant relationship with customer Preference but value of correlation is 0.296 which indicates that relation between these variables is weak.

H3: Social Recognition has a significant relationship with customer preference.

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As value of significance and correlation is 0.000 and 0.473, base on that we can conclude that social recognition is positively correlated with customer preference. Moreover, value of correlation which is 0.473 also suggests that the relationship is significant between these variables.

H4: Consumer ethnocentrism has a significant relationship with customer preference.

The significance value for Consumer ethnocentrism and customer Preference is 0.025 which states that there is a correlation between the variables. As the correlation is positive and have a value of 0.134 (lowest among all the variables) so we can concludes that customer preference has very weak relationship with customer preference.

H5: Unavailable Local Substitutes significant relationship with customer preference.

The value of significance between unavailable local substitutes and customer Preference is 0.000 which is < 0.05 , this indicates the relationship is exist between these variable. Correlation value is 0.467 which suggests that if unavailable local substitutes rise by one there will be substantial change on customer preference.

H6: Religiosity has a significant relationship with customer preference.

The value of significance is in the range of acceptance that is $0.000 < 0.05$, so we can state that Religiosity has a significant relationship with customer preference. Correlation value of religiosity is highest among all the other variables which indicates that religiosity is more associated with customer preference except others.

The significance value for the theoretical framework is equal to zero and F value is equal 34.91 indicating that the is model is significant and all six independent variables that are quality assurance, country of origin, social recognition, consumer ethnocentrism, unavailable local substitutes and religiosity are explaining 43.4% variation on dependent variable that is customer preference. On the other hand, remaining 56.6% effect is unexplained, some can test or may be test in other research or other variables can identify through literature.

H7: Quality assurance has a significant impact on customer preference

Sine, the value of significance is equal to 0.02 which is < 0.05 signifying that quality assurance has significant impact on customer preference. B is equal to 0.128 indicating that if the quality assurance change by one that will impact on customer preference by .128 or 12.8%.

H8: Country of Origin has a significant impact on customer preference.

The significance value of country of origin is $0.07 > 0.05$ and t value is also < 2 this indicates that country of origin has no impact on customer preference; hence we can reject the alternative hypothesis and accept the null hypothesis.

H9: Social Recognition has a significant impact on customer preference

Since the significance value is < 0.05 so we have enough evidence to accept the alternative hypothesis that is social recognition has a significant impact on customer preference. Here value of beta is 0.183 signifying that if social recognition increases by one this will impact on customer preference by 18.3%.

H10: Consumer ethnocentrism has a significant impact on customer preference.

As the level of significance is 0.210 which is > 0.05 explicates that consumer ethnocentrism has no impact on customer preference. Also the t-statistic value is on the low side that is -1.256 so we can reject the alternate hypothesis.

H11: Unavailable Local Substitutes has a significant impact on customer preference.

The value of significance is equal 0.006 which is < 0.05 indicating that unavailable local substitutes has significant effect on customer preference. Moreover, increase on unavailability of local substitutes will enhance the customer preference towards imported products by 15%.

H12: Religiosity has a significant impact on customer preference.

Given that in table as the value of significance is 0.000 which is under 0.05 and β is positive 0.300 so we can say that religiosity has a positive impact on customer preference. In the construct the religiosity is the factor which has highest t value that is 5.423 and β (0.300) so we conclude that this is the factor which has more influenced on customer preference or this is the strong influencer factor of customer preference.

Regression Line

Customer Preference = $.478 + .128\text{Quality Assurance} + .183\text{Soical Recognition} + .150\text{Unavailbe Local Substitutes} + .300\text{Religioisty}$
Religiosity is a very strong predictor of purchase intention as its value is the highest amongst all the other variables. Country of origin and Consumer ethnocentrism are insignificant because the level of significance is above 0.05 and they do not have any impact on customer preference. The middle predictors of the framework are social recognition and unavailable local substitutes that are .183 and 0.150; the weak predictor is quality assurance which is 0.128.

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Discussion

The key objective of the study is to explore the factors which influence customer preference while purchasing either local or imported beauty or personal healthcare products and to find out a significance relationship and impact of independent variables on dependent variable that is Customer Preference. Moreover, descriptive frequency test has been sprinted on the demographic profile of the respondents to identify the frequency and percentage of the respondents' age and gender. The age bracket we were focusing was arraying between 20-35 years, no response below or above the desired range has been entertained and the total numbers of participants were 280 out of which 224 were female candidates and 56 males. Secondly, correlation test that has been performed to find out the relationship together with the frequency of relationship among all the variables. Lastly, linear regression test has taken into consideration to check whether the impact of independent variables has existed or not either positive or negative.

For the research the sample size taken was 280 based on multivariate analysis, considered 40 respondents against each factor altogether the sample size we got is 280 (40 respondents * 7 variables). Further, sample size has been divided based on gender demographic and the ratio selected for this study was 20:80 Males/Females. Higher number of percentage assigned to females because of the nature of the industry and the usage of products from which this study is derived from. Moreover, data is collected from targeted population of women (224) and men (56) using or purchasing either local or imported beauty or personal healthcare products and could be generalized to the population of Karachi only. In this study, 148 respondents are from the age group of 20-25 years, while 85 respondents belong from 26-30 years whereas 52 lie in the age bracket of 31-35, this shows that the most of the respondents are from young group.

Proceed to this with the help of correlation analysis we test the hypothesis and the frequency of relationship between depended variable (customer preference) and independent variables (quality assurance, country of origin, social recognition, consumer ethnocentrism, unavailable local substitutes and religiosity). From the above table, the analysis of correlation shows that all the independent variables have significant relationship with customer preference (DV) therefore, we accept the H1 that is quality assurance has a significant relationship with customer preference with a value of 47.6%. This indicates to divert the attention of the customers towards local products companies need to have an edge of quality or maintain much standard of quality which will result in term of increased profits. The second variable is country of origin is correlated with customer preference having a value of 0.293 so we have enough evidence to accept the hypothesis that is Country of Origin has a significant relationship with customer preference. The result shows to some extent social recognition has better correction with customer preference like quality assurance has, the value of correction is 0.473 or 47.3%. Hence we can accept the H3 social recognition has a significant relationship with customer preference, now here companies need to provide the products which is acceptable in social circle, society or is equivalent to the lifestyle of the target customers. Moreover, from the results obtained, it is observed that consumer ethnocentrism is also correlated with customer preference with having a value of 0.134 or 13.4% so, we can accept the alternative hypothesis (H4) i.e. Consumer ethnocentrism has a significant relationship with customer preference but here the relationship between these two is very weak considering with the other variables. The H5 that is unavailable local substitute has significant relationship with customer preference is also in acceptable range as the significance level is 0.000 with correlation value of 46.7% nearly equal to the value of H1 and H3. Despite being mentioned at the end, religiosity is a variable which has a very strong relationship with customer preference obtained in the model with having a very high value of correlation that is 0.481 or 48.1%.

Furthermore, to check the impact of independent variable regression and Anova test has applied which has proven the acceptance and rejection of these H7, H8, H9, H10, H11 & H12. From the above table of model summary, R^2 is 0.43 which suggests that stated independent variables in the study is explaining 43% variation on dependent variable remaining 57% is not explained by the model which some can test in other research along with this the F is 34.913 depicts that all independent variables except country of origin and consumer ethnocentrism are statistically significant and predicts dependent variable. Further, it is proven that quality assurance, social recognition, unavailable local substitutes and religiosity have a significant impact on customer preference. The sig value of first variable quality assurance is 0.02 and $\beta = .128$ suggests that if quality assurance will change by one this will impact on customer preference by 12.8% hence we can accept the H7, parallel to this the other influencer is social recognition which has a sig value <0.05 along with the value of $\beta = 18.3\%$, based on this H9 has also been accepted. The H11 and H12 is accepted as well because their sig values lies in the acceptable range which are 0.06 and 0.00 respectively. However, religiosity is a variable which has highest beta value amongst all the acceptable variables which is 0.3 or 30%, this indicates that 30% fluctuation on dependent variable can occur by a marginal change in religiosity factor.

7. CONCLUSION & MARKETING IMPLICATIONS

We find that consumers with a larger amount of ethnocentrism direct the relationship between the quality of an item and states of mind toward international items. Consumer ethnocentrism have increased impressive consideration in strategic marketing

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writing as parts of outside item buy conduct. This study researched the impact of purchaser ethnocentrism on repurchase purpose. Past reviews recommended that consumer ethnocentrism was decidedly identified with customer animosity. In parallel with the past reviews, we recognized a huge and connection between customer ethnocentrism. Be that as it may, consumer ethnocentrism was observed to be contrarily identified with inclinations for the sampling.

We find that perceived quality has a critical and positive impact on mentalities toward international items. This research supports the literature: consumers put a higher esteem on international brands since they accept that these brands are of better quality and convey more prominent brilliance. Social status does not seem to significantly affect mentalities toward international items. This might be on the grounds that a few consumers relate local items with more prominent prestige than international items. Domestic brands have a tendency to reflect nearby cultural values and speak to validity and social standing.

Our discoveries indicate an opposite relationship between country of origin and states of mind toward international items. A likely explanation behind this is cultural measurements, for example, independence and socialism additionally impact the country-of-origin impact on behaviors toward international items. This study inspects consumers' recognitions towards the affirmation halal element utilized as a part of health and beauty care products. The review affirms that there is a critical relationship between respondents' religion and their recognitions towards these items. It was likewise found that the mean consumers' recognitions towards these items were noteworthy, which could clarify that our respondents who are worried about the halal component are additionally worried about the fixings utilized.

This study likewise gives an account of how consumers in Pakistan settle on buy choices as for religiosity calculate. The relationship between religious conviction and states of mind toward international items shows that numerous consumers are probably going to abstain from purchasing international brands out of a solid feeling of religiosity. In addition, this will shift contingent upon the quality of the consumer's religious conviction. Religion is a component of culture that plagues each part of a general public. Consequently, its impact on conduct can't be disparaged by advertisers. Cultural measurements are exceptionally progressive in a general public, however religious principles shape a steady and static column in the general public. Once the essentials of a religion have been gotten a handle on, the worldwide advertiser can be guaranteed they won't change very as often as possible.

The discoveries demonstrated that the opportunity to purchase imported items expanded with inaccessibility of neighborhood substitutes. It can be inferred that inaccessibility of neighborhood substitutes expands the possibility of obtaining outside items. The respondents concurred that the inclination to purchase remote items is expanding when nearby substitute are inaccessible. Respondents clarified that when there were no privately made items they tend to buy substitutes imported items. The respondents found that if there is a lack substitutes in nearby market, consumers propensity of obtaining imported items quickens. Neighborhood markets ought to, in this way differentiate their items to decrease consumer's opportunity to choose imported items.

Our discoveries are, however, restricted by the respondent of the study. The review was directed in Karachi utilizing convenience based sampling techniques, which infers that its results can't be summed up all over Pakistan. Future research on this subject could, in this manner, consider not only the way of life of the general public being concentrated, additionally culturally diverse correlations of consumer conduct. Furthermore, while we have utilized cross-sectional information and analyzed causal components with hypothesis in view of people's self-reported views about their behavior, future research could utilize a blend of various methodologies (quantitative and qualitative) and more target strategies for information gathering, for example, tests.

The findings additionally demonstrate an adjustment in consumer opinions towards products originated from outside nations in light of the past findings. The developing of economy and country's exertion in innovative and monetary improvement appears to be very impact how purchaser began to have ideal recognitions towards international country picture, item quality and its image nature.

Marketing Implications

This study will enable the markets in Karachi to determine the proportion to which youngsters prefer international and domestic beauty products. It will also let them understand the factors due to which the consumers are more attracted towards international beauty products in comparison to the local products. From the results of this study, the marketers can change their business strategy to include those factors in the local products which consumers search in international products. A researchers we hope that this paper to be exceptionally valuable to businesses and advertisers particularly who coordinate directly with the international nations as a product and service origins, paying little heed to the business purposes; whether in exchanging, fabricating or even in product development and advancement.

It seems that quality of the international products play a vital role in the customer preference. In future, the local beauty products company can benefit from this study to determine the factors to include in the local beauty products. This study can also

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be used as a starting point for other researchers who are looking to search on the similar issue. This study will assist those researchers to determine which factors were a complete failure in the study. Hence, they can be excluded from the future studies.

This study can assist the marketing management of the local beauty product companies to analyze how well they can market their products as per the standard of international products in order to attract the consumers. This study will also work as a guide to the local beauty products manufacturers in relation to what quality material they should use in the manufacturing of the beauty products, so that they can give the same satisfactory results as the international products. Lastly, this study can also be used as a starting point for the similar study on the country level since majority of the beauty products population lives in Karachi.

For worldwide marketers it is suggested to give assets and time on comprehension religious convictions before arriving another market, especially where Islam is the confidence of the greater part. Studying the effect of religion on the esteem frameworks of a general public what's more, the impact of significant worth frameworks on promoting must not be given less attention.

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